

BPaaS Execution in CloudSocket

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Abstract. The H2020 research CloudSocket project enacts the business IT-alignment by implementing Business process as a Service (BPaaS)

1 Introduction

Cloud Computing has a still growing influence on the IT ecosystem, especially for business applications. Still challenging is the so-called *business and IT alignment (BITA)*. BITA bridges the gap between the business and IT domains and ensures sufficient and the right hardware/software resources are available to handle a company's business processes. We consider BITA as one of the key success factors for cloud usage. For supporting BITA in clouds, the current application centric view needs to be enhanced with a corresponding *business process (BP)* view. The CloudSocket project³ enables such a BP-oriented view on cloud offerings and supports cloud-enabled BITA. In particular, it implements BITA by offering a new cloud service level: *Business process as a Service (BPaaS)* [3].

CloudSocket provides a brokerage platform for BPaaS. A CloudSocket Broker plans and designs the BPs, implements executable *workflows (WFs)* and creates *BPaaS Bundles*. The BPaaS Bundles are deployable in the cloud and offered by a CloudSocket Broker to its customers through a marketplace.

2 CloudSocket Architecture

The CloudSocket architecture builds upon the four loosely coupled buildings blocks shown in Figure 1.

The *Design Environment* creates the BPaaS Design Package by editing domain specific BP models and executable WF models, mapping a domain specific BP model to an executable WF model as well as semantically annotating BP and WF models. The Design Environment is based on ADONIS⁴.

The *Allocation Environment* enriches the executable WF of the BPaaS Design Package with concrete and deployable cloud services. The cloud services are modelled in CAMEL [2] and included in the BPaaS Bundle. Design and Allocation Environment compose a management environment assisting the broker in managing the BPaaS offerings.

³ <https://www.cloudsocket.eu/>

⁴ <http://en.adonis-community.com/>

Fig. 1. The CloudSocket Architecture

The *Execution Environment* offers BPaaS Bundles via a marketplace to End-Users. As a Bundle is purchased, Cloudiator [1] orchestrates, monitors and adapts the cloud services. End-Users interact with the services via the WF Engine⁵. Based on the semantic enrichment in the management environments, the Execution Environment can operate on a semantically enriched BPaaS Bundle.

The *Evaluation Environment* provides optimisation suggestions (KPI assessment, optimised BPaaS deployment and adaptation patterns) to the Broker by abstracting technical data back to domain specific business decision.

Currently CloudSocket reaches the first half of the project with the release of the 1st prototype⁶, enabling the holistic BPaaS life cycle.

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References

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⁵ <https://www.cloudsocket.eu/group/guest/wiki/-/wiki/Main/Workflow+Engine+Component>

⁶ <https://www.cloudsocket.eu/group/guest/wiki/-/wiki/Main/Components>